

CINDERELA List of waste codes with potential for Secondary Raw Materials in construction.

EWC Code 2	EWC Code	Description
01 01	10102	wastes from mineral non-metalliferous excavation
01 03	10308	dusty and powdery wastes other than those mentioned in 01 03 07
01 04	10408	waste gravel and crushed rocks other than those mentioned in 01 04 07
01 04	10409	waste sand and clays
01 04	10410	dusty and powdery wastes other than those mentioned in 01 04 07
01 04	10413	wastes from stone cutting and sawing other than those mentioned in 01 04 07
01 05	10504	freshwater drilling muds and wastes
02 01	20103	plant-tissue waste
02 03	20304	materials unsuitable for consumption or processing
03 03	30301	waste bark and wood
03 03	30302	green liquor sludge (from recovery of cooking liquor)
03 03	30305	de-inking sludges from paper recycling
03 03	30309	lime mud waste
03 03	30310	fibre rejects, fibre-, filler- and coating-sludges from mechanical separation
03 03	30311	sludges from on-site effluent treatment other than those mentioned in 03 03 10
07 06	70699	wastes not otherwise specified
10 01	100101	bottom ash, slag and boiler dust (excluding boiler dust mentioned in 10 01 04)
10 01	100102	coal fly ash
10 01	100103	fly ash from peat and untreated wood
10 01	100105	calcium-based reaction wastes from flue-gas desulphurisation in solid form
10 01	100107	calcium-based reaction wastes from flue-gas desulphurisation in sludge form
10 01	100115	bottom ash, slag and boiler dust from co-incineration other than those mentioned in 10 01 14

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10 01	100117	fly ash from co-incineration other than those mentioned in 10 01 16
10 01	100119	wastes from gas cleaning other than those mentioned in 10 01 05, 10 01 07 and 10 01 18
10 01	100121	sludges from on-site effluent treatment other than those mentioned in 10 01 20
10 01	100123	aqueous sludges from boiler cleansing other than those mentioned in 10 01 22
10 01	100124	sands from fluidised beds
10 01	100125	wastes from fuel storage and preparation of coal-fired power plants
10 01	100126	wastes from cooling-water treatment
10 01	100199	wastes not otherwise specified
10 02	100201	wastes from the processing of slag
10 02	100202	unprocessed slag
10 02	100208	solid wastes from gas treatment other than those mentioned in 10 02 07
10 02	100210	mill scales
10 02	100212	wastes from cooling-water treatment other than those mentioned in 10 02 11
10 02	100214	sludges and filter cakes from gas treatment other than those mentioned in 10 02 13
10 02	100215	other sludges and filter cakes
10 02	100299	wastes not otherwise specified
10 03	100316	skimmings other than those mentioned in 10 03 15
10 03	100330	wastes from treatment of salt slags and black drosses other than those mentioned in 10 03 29
10 09	100903	furnace slag
10 09	100906	casting cores and moulds which have not undergone pouring other than those
10 09	100908	casting cores and moulds which have undergone pouring other than those
10 09	100910	flue-gas dust other than those mentioned in 10 09 09
10 09	100912	other particulates other than those mentioned in 10 09 11
10 09	100914	waste binders other than those mentioned in 10 09 13
10 09	100916	waste crack-indicating agent other than those mentioned in 10 09 15
10 09	100999	wastes not otherwise specified

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10 10	101003	furnace slag
10 11	101105	particulates and dust
10 11	101110	waste preparation mixture before thermal processing, other than those.....
10 11	101112	waste glass other than those mentioned in 10 11 11
10 11	101114	glass-polishing and -grinding sludge other than those mentioned in 10 11 13
10 11	101116	solid wastes from flue-gas treatment other than those mentioned in 10 11 15
10 11	101118	sludges and filter cakes from flue-gas treatment other than those mentioned in 10 11 17
10 11	101120	solid wastes from on-site effluent treatment other than those mentioned in 10 11 19
10 11	101199	wastes not otherwise specified
10 12	101208	waste ceramics, bricks, tiles and construction products (after thermal processing)
10 12	101208	waste ceramics, bricks, tiles and construction products (after thermal processing)
10 12	101210	solid wastes from gas treatment other than those mentioned in 10 12 09
10 12	101299	wastes not otherwise specified
12 01	120101	ferrous metal filings and turnings
12 01	120102	ferrous metal dust and particles
12 01	120103	non-ferrous metal filings and turnings
12 01	120104	non-ferrous metal dust and particles
12 01	120105	plastics shavings and turnings
12 01	120117	waste blasting material other than those mentioned in 12 01 16
15 01	150102	plastic packaging
15 01	150105	composite packaging
15 01	150107	glass packaging
15 01	150109	textile packaging
16 10	161004	aqueous concentrates other than those mentioned in 16 10 03
16 11	161104	other linings and refractories from metallurgical processes other than those
17 01	170101	concrete

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EWC Code 2	EWC Code	Description
17 01	170102	bricks
17 01	170103	tiles and ceramics
17 01	170107	mixtures of concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics other than those mentioned in 17 01 06
17 02	170201	wood
17 02	170202	glass
17 02	170203	plastic
17 03	170302	bituminous mixtures other than those mentioned in 17 03 01
17 05	170504	soil and stones other than those mentioned in 17 05 03
17 05	170506	dredging spoil other than those mentioned in 17 05 05
17 05	170508	track ballast other than those mentioned in 17 05 07
17 06	170604	insulation materials other than those mentioned in 17 06 01 and 17 06 03
17 08	170802	gypsum-based construction materials other than those mentioned in 17 08 01
17 09	170904	mixed construction and demolition wastes other than those mentioned in 17 09 01, 17 09 02 and 17 09 03
19 01	190112	bottom ash and slag other than those mentioned in 19 01 11
19 05	190502	non-composted fraction of animal and vegetable waste
19 05	190503	off-specification compost
19 06	190604	digestate from anaerobic treatment of municipal waste
19 06	190606	digestate from anaerobic treatment of animal and vegetable waste
19 08	190801	screenings
19 08	190802	waste from desanding
19 08	190805	sludges from treatment of urban waste water
19 08	190814	sludges from other treatment of industrial waste water other than those mentioned in 19 08 13
19 12	191204	plastic and rubber
19 12	191205	glass
19 12	191208	textiles
19 12	191209	minerals (for example sand, stones)

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19 12	191212	other wastes (including mixtures of materials) from mechanical treatment of wastes other than those mentioned in 19 12 11
20 01	200102	glass
20 01	200110	clothes
20 01	200111	textiles
20 01	200138	wood other than that mentioned in 20 01 37
20 01	200139	plastics
20 02	200202	soil and stones
20 02	200203	other non-biodegradable wastes
20 03	200303	street-cleaning residues
20 03	200306	waste from sewage cleaning